

Managing Editor's Column

Dear Readers:

Here is the first "real" issue of J.UCS, the Journal of Universal Computer Science, J.UCS 1, 1 (1995).

It consists of 5 papers selected from 14 submitted ones on the basis of at least 2 positive referees' reports per paper. I hope you will enjoy the papers. It is good to see that the papers submitted cover a wide range of topics: from computer arithmetic (Fenwick), to algorithms on trees (Leppanen), to the problem of "semi-anonymity" in networks (Flinn et al.), to random strings (Calude), to the importance of shuffle operations (Paun et al.).

If you have any comments concerning J.UCS please let me know! Not that J.UCS is just the first of a number of journals that will appear in the same format, and hence cross-referenceable. Also a number of books will be incorporated in what we have started to call our electronic library.

Yours sincerely

Hermann Maurer, Managing Editor
Graz University of Technology,
Graz / Austria, January 28, 1995.
email: hmaurer@iicm.tu-graz.ac.at

P.S.: J.UCS 1, 2 (1995), the next issue, will appear February 28, 1995 on the server <http://iicm.tu-graz.ac.at> and will be distributed from there to other servers. Those servers that are both publicly accessible and currently active can be found in the public server list.